

Motivation and its determinants among community pharmacists in Vietnam: insights and intervention opportunities from network analysis

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Received 14 April 2025 ♦ Accepted 16 May 2025 ♦ Published 9 June 2025

Citation: Tran BK, Van CK, Huynh TTH, Duong KH, Lanh NV, Nguyen THT (2025) Motivation and its determinants among community pharmacists in Vietnam: insights and intervention opportunities from network analysis. *Pharmacia* 72: 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.72.e155839>

Abstract

This study was conducted to assess the intrinsic, organisational, and sociocultural motivational factors of community pharmacists. A cross-sectional survey was conducted among 437 community pharmacists in Vietnam. The interactions between motivational factors were visually depicted using network analysis. Compared to organisational factors (4.00) and sociocultural factors (3.98), pharmacist motivation mainly came from intrinsic factors (4.04). Intrinsic motivation was significantly higher among those who were single, widowed or divorced ($p = 0.025$); working in pharmacies or pharmacy chains ($p = 0.032$); and in urban areas ($p = 0.027$). Supervision, work pride and internal recognition were the most central factors in the motivational network. These findings suggest that future research and interventions targeting supervision, work pride and internal recognition may generate a spillover effect—producing broader impacts across the motivational system, thereby improving work motivation.

Keywords

motivation, organisational factors, sociocultural factors, intrinsic factors, community pharmacists

Introduction

Human resources are a significant factor affecting the quality of health care and public health outcomes (Nwankwo et al. 2024). Despite their critical importance,

the World Health Organization estimates that there will be a shortage of about 11 million health workers globally by 2030, mainly in low- and lower-middle-income countries (World Health Organization n.d.). Vietnam experiences similar challenges and faces a shortage of health

workers due to various factors such as high training costs, brain drain, resignations caused by low wages, long working hours, and the impact of COVID-19 (Le et al. 2024a).

In Vietnam, in the pharmaceutical sector, the number of pharmacists is 3.41 per 10,000 people, which is lower than that of Thailand (5.07), Singapore (5.03), and the Philippines (3.48), according to 2016 data (Our World in Data n.d.). The target for the 2025–2030 period is for Vietnam to reach a ratio of 4.0 pharmacists per 10,000 people (Ministry of Health of Vietnam 2025), indicating an urgent need to improve both the quantity and quality of training. Meanwhile, the density of pharmacies in Vietnam per 100,000 people is four times higher than the global average (Tran et al. 2024). With the rapid increase in recent years of pharmacy chains owned by retail corporations, the pharmaceutical retail market in Vietnam is facing fierce competition (Nguyen and Le 2024). A report from Vietnam shows that there are seven pharmacy chains with more than 3,000 stores and a total revenue of USD 1.1 billion, accounting for more than 50% of the market share among a total of 60,000 pharmacies nationwide (Vietdata's 2023 Pharmaceutical Retail Chains Industry Report n.d.). However, access to qualified pharmacists remains difficult, and pharmacies may be poorly managed, especially in poor or rural areas (Beardsley et al. 2023).

Previous research in Vietnam found that more than half of community pharmacists occasionally felt work-related tiredness, with one-third feeling exhausted at the end of the workday (Le et al. 2024b). This study also reported that the prevalence of personal, work-related and client-related burnout was 12.7%, 12.4% and 11.6%, respectively (Le et al. 2024b). High levels of work stress can significantly reduce work motivation, as energy is easily depleted, leading to burnout and undermining employees' confidence in their career success (Putra et al. 2023). In contrast, pharmacists who did not experience burnout expressed a sense of professional fulfilment, which motivated them to provide patient-centred care (Walker et al. 2025). This suggests that psychological stress may negatively impact the performance and career commitment of community pharmacists.

Health systems in developing countries increasingly need to strengthen their human resources to help achieve the Millennium Development Goals (Willis-Shattuck et al. 2008). One major barrier to achieving these goals is the lack of a sufficiently motivated and competent workforce (Willis-Shattuck et al. 2008). Motivation refers to the degree to which an individual is willing to exert and sustain effort to support the goals of the organisation (Tegegne et al. 2024). Employee motivation is a key factor in retaining top talent in any organisation, especially where organisational success heavily depends on it (Slimane 2017). Previous research has identified several factors that motivate community pharmacists to continue their work despite challenges (Asghar et al. 2024). These include a high level of education, a wide range of employment opportunities, flexible schedules, direct patient interaction and a positive impact on sales (Asghar et al. 2024).

Studies from around the world have explored community pharmacists' motivation in relation to specific activities—such as reporting suspected adverse drug reactions

in Portugal (Ferreira-da-Silva et al. 2023), providing high-quality pharmaceutical care in Belgium (Saevels et al. 2023), and offering services to drug misusers in Scotland (Matheson and Bond 2011). Additionally, the influence of intrinsic motivations and extrinsic rewards has been examined across various pharmacy workplace contexts in the United States (Gist-Mackey et al. 2024). In Vietnam, while hospital pharmacists were reported to be highly motivated, there is still limited research on the motivation of community pharmacists (Hoat et al. 2024). Therefore, this study was conducted to assess the intrinsic, organisational and sociocultural motivational factors of community pharmacists in Vietnam.

Methods

Study design and setting

A cross-sectional, Google Form-based survey was conducted among community pharmacists in Vietnam. There are two common types of drug outlets in Vietnam. The first is pharmacies (Nhà thuốc), which represent the highest level of drug outlet and must be registered under pharmacists who hold a bachelor's degree in pharmacy. The second type is drug counters (Quầy thuốc), which are licensed to pharmacy personnel with lower qualifications, such as a college diploma or secondary diploma in pharmacy (Beardsley et al. 2023). The survey period was from January to April 2025. This study was approved by the Institutional Review Board of the Hospital of Vietnam National University, Hanoi (Approval No. 01/2025/BVĐQGHN-HĐĐĐ). Participants confirmed their consent by selecting "I agree" after reading an online information sheet. Data were collected anonymously via a secure online platform, and no personal identifiers were stored.

Study population and data collection

The sample size of this study was estimated using the Sample Size Calculator by Raosoft, Inc. (Raosoft Inc. n.d.). With a margin of error of 5%, a confidence level of 95%, a response distribution of 50%, and a population size of 82,000 pharmacists (Nguyen et al. 2021), the required sample size was calculated to be 383. A convenience sampling technique was used to recruit participants. The inclusion criteria were licensed community pharmacists who were able to read and understand Vietnamese. Exclusion criteria included trainees and students who were interns.

Community pharmacists were recruited by sending invitations to participate in the online survey through a Zalo group (a popular social network in Vietnam), which was created to facilitate communication among members participating in a course on the continuous updating of pharmaceutical professional knowledge for community pharmacists, organised by a pharmacy college in Vietnam. A total of 480 students participated in these courses during the survey period.

Questionnaire

The motivation of community pharmacists was assessed using a tool developed by Malik et al. (2018), which measures three key dimensions: intrinsic, organisational, and sociocultural motivation. Intrinsic motivation was evaluated through 20 items across six domains, including work interest, personal values, and self-actualisation. Organisational motivation was assessed with 34 items spanning areas such as working conditions, supervision, and incentives. Sociocultural motivation was measured using 12 items related to interpersonal relationships, social recognition, and personal life issues. The motivation score for each dimension was calculated as the average of its corresponding items, with higher scores indicating higher levels of motivation among participants.

The translation and cultural adaptation of the questionnaire followed the guidelines of Beaton et al. (2000). The questionnaire was independently translated into Vietnamese by two bilingual translators (one with a pharmacy background and one with a linguistics background) and then merged into a single version. This version was then back-translated into English by two pharmacy experts who were unaware of the original version to check for accuracy. A panel of pharmacy experts and a medical English instructor assessed content equivalence. The pre-final version was piloted on 20 people, and the feedback obtained was used to refine the final Vietnamese version of the questionnaire. The reliability of the intrinsic, organisational, and sociocultural motivation scales was 0.97, 0.98, and 0.96, respectively, indicating high reliability.

Data analysis

Data were entered and analysed using SPSS version 22.0. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation were used to present the results. The normality of the data distribution was tested using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test, the Shapiro–Wilk test, and Q–Q plots. Mann–Whitney and Kruskal–Wallis tests were used to compare motivation scores among retailers based on different demographic variables. A significance level of $p < 0.05$ was used to determine statistically significant associations in all the above-mentioned tests.

Network analysis provides a set of tools for visually mapping the relationships between interacting components, and it has become one of the important methods for understanding complex systems, such as those found in health behaviour research (Mkhitarian et al. 2019; Saqr et al. 2024). Compared with traditional methods such as regression analysis and factor analysis, network analysis allows for the examination of complex relationships among multiple variables simultaneously (Weiß et al. 2023). By identifying the most central nodes in the network, the analysis results can inform future interventions (Likhanov et al. 2022). In this study, network analysis was used to describe the relationships between motivational components among pharmacists. Network analysis was performed using R software (version 4.1.1). First, the Spearman correlation matrix was

used to determine the relationships between factors. Then, the LASSO technique—a method for model selection and simplification—was applied to construct a network that showed the strongest relationships between factors. The network model was selected based on the EBIC criterion ($\gamma = 0.5$) and visualised using the “qgraph” software package. To assess the stability of the relationships in the network (i.e., the links between factors) and the centrality of each factor, the bootnet package was used. A non-parametric bootstrap method was applied to generate 1000 random samples to test the stability of the relationships.

Results

The mean age of the participants was 35.71 years (SD = 7.89). The majority of participants were women (86.0%) and married (88.8%). Nearly 60% of the participants worked in rural areas, worked at pharmacies, and had an average monthly income of 5 to 9 million VND (Table 1). The motivation scores for intrinsic, organisational, and sociocultural factors were 4.04, 4.00, and 3.98, respectively. When considering each factor individually—motivation scores were calculated as the average of corresponding items—two intrinsic factors, level of work interest (4.12) and intrinsic satisfaction (4.11), had the highest scores (Table 2).

Table 1. Demographic and occupational characteristics of study participants (n = 437).

Characteristics	n	%	
Gender	Woman	376	86.0
	Man	61	14.0
Age group (year)	< 35	226	51.7
	≥ 35	211	48.3
Marital status	Married	388	88.8
	Single/widowed/divorced	49	11.2
Type of pharmacy	Drug counter	271	62.0
	Pharmacy/chain pharmacy	166	38.0
Area	Rural	263	60.2
	Urban	174	39.8
Type of employment	Part-time	109	24.9
	Full-time	328	75.1
Working hours per day	< 8	36	8.2
	8	63	14.4
	8–10	100	22.9
	> 10	238	54.5
Years of working experience	< 3	132	30.2
	3–4	100	22.9
	≥ 5	205	46.9
Pharmacy education level	Intermediate level	95	21.7
	College	217	49.7
	University/postgraduate	125	28.6
Availability of job description for current position	Yes	346	79.2
	No	91	20.8
Position	Staff	238	54.5
	Manager	199	45.5
Monthly income (million VND)	< 5	112	25.6
	5–9	256	58.6
	≥ 10	69	15.8

Table 2. Motivational factors of study participants (n = 437).

Motivation	Motivation score	Standard deviation
Intrinsic factors	4.04	0.55
Basic needs	3.80	0.76
Personal values	4.09	0.58
Level of work interest	4.12	0.59
Work pride and internal recognition	4.04	0.60
Self-actualisation and esteem	4.07	0.59
Intrinsic satisfaction	4.11	0.55
Organisational factors	4.00	0.37
Working conditions and facilities	3.96	0.53
Job roles	4.05	0.53
Health and safety	4.04	0.51
Pay	3.99	0.54
Incentives	4.00	0.54
Resource availability	3.97	0.55
Supervision	4.00	0.53
Socio-cultural factors	3.98	0.50
Work-related interpersonal relationships	3.95	0.53
Social recognition	3.97	0.55
Personal life issues	4.02	0.51

Intrinsic motivation was significantly higher among those who were single, widowed, or divorced ($p = 0.025$); worked in a pharmacy or pharmacy chain ($p = 0.032$); and lived in urban areas ($p = 0.027$). Organisational motivation was significantly higher among those who were single, widowed, or divorced ($p = 0.038$); had a college degree ($p = 0.014$); and had a job description ($p = 0.004$). Sociocultural motivation was significantly higher among those who had a college degree ($p = 0.016$) and had a job description ($p = 0.013$) (Table 3).

Table 3. Differences in intrinsic, organisational, and sociocultural motivation factors by participants' demographic and occupational characteristics (n = 437).

Characteristics	Intrinsic factors		Organisational factors		Sociocultural factors		
	Mean (SD)	Mean Rank	Mean (SD)	Mean Rank	Mean (SD)	Mean Rank	
Marital status	Married	4 (0.27)	214.27	4 (0.19)	214.55	4 (0.11)	217.01
	Single/widowed/divorced	4.03 (0.61)	256.47	4.02 (0.41)	254.24	4 (0.27)	234.77
<i>p</i> value		0.025		0.038		0.322	
Type of pharmacy	Drug counter	4 (0.23)	208.98	4 (0.19)	217.33	4 (0.08)	220.84
	Pharmacy/chain pharmacy	4 (0.44)	235.36	4 (0.27)	221.72	4 (0.17)	216.00
<i>p</i> value		0.032		0.724		0.678	
Area	Rural	4 (0.21)	208.31	4 (0.18)	212.66	4 (0.11)	214.88
	Urban	4 (0.45)	235.16	4 (0.27)	228.58	4 (0.11)	225.23
<i>p</i> value		0.027		0.196		0.370	
Pharmacy education level	Secondary diploma	4 (0.21)	192.32	3.98 (0.25)	192.85	4 (0.17)	197.21
	College diploma	4 (0.24)	223.25	4 (0.22)	235.76	4 (0)	234.88
	Bachelor's degree or higher	4 (0.49)	231.90	4 (0.27)	209.77	4 (0.17)	207.99
<i>p</i> value		0.051		0.014		0.016	
Availability of job description for current position	Yes	4 (0.28)	202.90	3.97 (0.37)	185.55	4 (0.17)	191.59
	No	4 (0.25)	223.24	4 (0.2)	227.80	4 (0.08)	226.21
<i>p</i> value		0.166		0.004		0.013	

Note: *p*-values were calculated using the Mann–Whitney test for comparisons between two groups and the Kruskal–Wallis test for comparisons among three or more groups. Bold values indicate statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$). All demographic and occupational variables were included in the analysis; however, only those with statistically significant associations with at least one motivational factor are presented in the table. Variables analyzed included age group, gender, marital status, pharmacy type, area of residence, employment type, daily working hours, years of experience, pharmacy education level, availability of a job description, position, and monthly income.

The network analysis showed that, based on an estimated 72 non-zero edges out of all 120 possible edges, the estimated network density was around 60%. Two factors in the organisational cluster had the highest positive correlation, indicated by the thickest blue edge between SV (supervision) and RA (resource availability) ($r_{\text{partial}} = 0.67$). Additionally, within the intrinsic cluster, the highest correlation was found between SE (self-actualisation and esteem) and WI (level of work interest) ($r_{\text{partial}} = 0.33$), while in the sociocultural cluster, IR (work-related interpersonal relationships) and PL (personal life issues) had the highest correlation ($r_{\text{partial}} = 0.39$) (Fig. 1).

There was a slight decrease in the values of expected influence and strength for the nodes when comparing the

Figure 1. Network analysis of motivational factors among study participants.

Figure 2. Network bootstrap procedure reflecting edge stability, betweenness, closeness, expected influence, and strength (A). Centrality of domains in the network (B). SV – supervision, WR – work pride and internal recognition, WI – level of work interest, IS – intrinsic satisfaction, IN – incentives, PY – pay, JR – job roles, RA – resource availability, HS – health and safety, SE – self-actualisation and esteem, PL – personal life issues, WF – working conditions and facilities, SR – social recognition, PV – personal values, IR – work-related interpersonal relationships, BN – basic needs.

subsample estimates with those from the full sample, as the subset size was reduced from 95% to 25% of the original sample (Fig. 2). The centrality index values of expected influence and strength were 0.75 and 0.60, respectively. However, for betweenness and closeness, the decrease was more pronounced, with centrality indices dropping to zero. The two most central factors in the motivational network were SV (supervision) and WR (work pride and internal recognition).

Discussion

Compared with organisational and sociocultural factors, intrinsic factors—with the highest scores—indicate that community pharmacists' motivation primarily stems from internal drivers. Organisational researchers have previously recognised that intrinsic motivation is a key determinant of work performance (Shin and Grant 2019). When examining each factor in more detail, the level of work interest had the highest score. When motivation originates from intrinsic factors, individuals find the work itself engaging, which leads to increased concentration, greater persistence, and a sense of fulfilment in the act of working (Shin and Grant 2019). Career interests reflect stable personal tendencies toward particular types of activities, work environments, and desired outcomes. These interests serve as motivational sources, prompting individuals to pursue career goals and professional achievements (Stepanek and Paul 2023).

Single, widowed, and divorced individuals exhibited higher intrinsic motivation than their married counterparts. Prior research has also found marital status to be associated with intrinsic motivation (Zhang et al. 2023).

Being single, divorced, or widowed has been linked with negative wellness indicators, including a higher likelihood of depression and burnout (Kang 2020). Individuals with past experiences of depression and emotional distress may also experience poorer health outcomes (Zhang et al. 2023). Nevertheless, such individuals often dedicate more energy to their work (Zhang et al. 2023).

Pharmacists working in chain or independent pharmacies demonstrated significantly higher levels of intrinsic motivation compared to those employed at drug counters ($p = 0.025$). Similarly, pharmacists working in urban areas also showed higher intrinsic motivation than their rural counterparts ($p = 0.027$). These two variables—pharmacy type and work location—are closely related in Vietnam, as pharmacies and pharmacy chains are predominantly located in urban areas, while drug counters are more common in rural settings. Urban environments typically offer more opportunities for education, career advancement, and higher income, which may enhance motivation. Previous research found that healthcare professionals in urban areas tend to have significantly higher job motivation and satisfaction (Grujicic et al. 2016), partly due to greater professional recognition (Grujicic et al. 2016). These findings suggest that improving working conditions—particularly in rural areas and drug counters—may increase intrinsic motivation, thereby enhancing pharmacy practice and healthcare service quality.

In the present study, the network analysis aimed to explore the interrelationships among motivational factors. Given the complexity of this method, only the principal findings are highlighted. The presence of 72 non-zero edges out of 120 possible (60%) indicates strong interconnections between the factors. These factors clustered

into three relatively distinct groups: intrinsic, organisational, and sociocultural. The centrality indices for expected influence (0.75) and strength (0.60) indicated stability, as they exceeded the recommended threshold of 0.50 (Epskamp and Fried 2018). A strength above 0.70 is considered a very large effect (Cohen 1988). In contrast, betweenness and closeness values dropped to zero, reflecting instability. Therefore, the interpretation of results prioritises expected influence and strength due to their high stability, in line with psychological network analysis recommendations (Epskamp et al. 2018).

Centrality analysis revealed that supervision was the most influential factor in terms of both expected influence and strength. This indicates its central role in motivating pharmacy staff. Interventions targeting supervision may have broad, positive effects throughout the motivational network. Workplace resources—particularly supervisory support—enhance employees' mental and physical energy, leading to greater engagement, satisfaction, and performance (Anasi 2020). Supervisors' integrity and accountability influence employee performance both directly and indirectly via workplace morale and engagement (De Carlo et al. 2020). In pharmacy practice, effective supervision not only helps pharmacists manage work-related challenges but also facilitates professional development (O'Byrne and Warren 2022). Since motivation is key to pharmacist retention and engagement, supervisors must use appropriate techniques to foster a supportive work environment (Donehew 1979). In practice, the results suggest that interventions aimed at improving supervision—such as leadership, communication, and management training—should be prioritised, as they target the most central and stable nodes, making them efficient strategies, particularly in resource-constrained settings like Vietnam.

Network centrality analysis also identified work pride and internal recognition as highly influential factors. Employees who are appropriately recognised feel valued by their organisation. When employers acknowledge and appreciate staff efforts, employees are more likely to work toward achieving organisational goals (Kumari et al. 2021). This finding aligns with a previous study reporting that 88.8% of pharmacists are strongly motivated by recognition, appreciation, and rewards (Al-Omar et al. 2022). Conversely, factors such as BN (basic needs), IR (interpersonal relationships), and PV (personal values) had much lower centrality indices, indicating peripheral roles in the network. If targeted individually, these may have limited capacity to generate wider motivational improvements.

Despite its strengths, this study has limitations. First, due to the convenience sampling method, most participants were from northern Vietnam (83.1%), with only 16.9% from the central and southern regions, potentially limiting generalisability. The centrality of supervision, work pride, and internal recognition may reflect region-specific attitudes. Thus, intervention strategies derived from this network should be further refined or tested using nationally representative samples before broader application. Future studies should explore whether these

findings are applicable to other healthcare worker populations. Additionally, the proposed intervention targets were not validated in this study, underscoring the need for future evaluations of their effectiveness. Qualitative research could also help explore regional differences in work motivation and their underlying causes.

Conclusion

The motivation of drug retailers primarily stems from intrinsic factors. Intrinsic motivation was significantly higher among individuals who were single, widowed, or divorced; worked in pharmacies or pharmacy chains; and lived in urban areas. Supervision and work pride/internal recognition emerged as the most central elements in the motivational network. These findings suggest that interventions targeting these two areas may generate broad and sustained improvements in pharmacists' motivation.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the support and collaboration of Hai Duong Central College of Pharmacy, Tra Vinh University, Can Tho University of Medicine and Pharmacy, and the participating pharmacists.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: Pharmacists gave their informed consent prior to their inclusion in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Funding

No funding was reported.

Author contributions

Conceptualization: BKT, CKV. Methodology: BKT, TTHH, NVL. Investigation: BKT, TTHH. Resources: BKT, KHD, THTN. Writing – original draft: BKT, CKV, TTHH, KHD, NVL, THTN. Writing – review & editing: BKT, CKV, TTHH, KHD, NVL, THTN.

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Data availability

The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding authors upon reasonable request.

References

- Al-Omar HA, Khurshid F, Sayed SK, Alotaibi WH, Almutairi RM, Arafah AM, Mansy W, Alshathry S (2022) Job motivation and satisfaction among female pharmacists working in private pharmacy professional sectors in Saudi Arabia. *Risk Management and Healthcare Policy* 15: 1383–1394. <https://doi.org/10.2147/RMHP.S369084>
- Anasi SN (2020) Perceived influence of work relationship, work load and physical work environment on job satisfaction of librarians in South-West, Nigeria. *Global Knowledge, Memory and Communication* 69(6/7): 377–398. <https://doi.org/10.1108/GKMC-11-2019-0135>
- Asghar S, Atif M, Arshad S (2024) An exploratory study to identify the factors influencing community pharmacist retention by using COM-B model. *Research in Social and Administrative Pharmacy* 20(8): 786–795. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sapharm.2024.05.001>
- Beardsley J, Chambers JM, Lam TT, Zawahir S, Le H, Nguyen TA, Walsh M, Thuy Van PT, Cam Van NT, Hoang TH, Mai Hung TT, Thai CH, Anh DD, Fox GJ (2023) Mapping access to drug outlets in Vietnam: distribution of drug outlets and the sociodemographic characteristics of the communities they serve. *The Lancet Regional Health - Western Pacific* 30: 100668. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lanwpc.2022.100668>
- Beaton DE, Bombardier C, Guillemin F, Ferraz MB (2000) Guidelines for the Process of Cross-Cultural Adaptation of Self-Report Measures. *Spine* 25(24): 3186–3191. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00007632-200012150-00014>
- Cohen J (1988) *Statistical power analysis for the behavioral sciences* (2nd edn.). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- De Carlo A, Dal Corso L, Carluccio F, Colledani D, Falco A (2020) Positive Supervisor Behaviors and Employee Performance: The Serial Mediation of Workplace Spirituality and Work Engagement. *Frontiers in Psychology* 11: 1834. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.01834>
- Donehew GR (1979) Motivating pharmacists. *Contemporary Pharmacy Practice* 2(4): 185–189.
- Epskamp S, Borsboom D, Fried EI (2018) Estimating psychological networks and their accuracy: A tutorial paper. *Behavior Research Methods* 50(1): 195–212. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13428-017-0862-1>
- Epskamp S, Fried EI (2018) A tutorial on regularized partial correlation networks. *Psychological Methods* 23(4): 617–634. <https://doi.org/10.1037/met0000167>
- Ferreira-da-Silva R, Alves JM, Vieira C, Silva AM, Marques J, Morato M, Polónia JJ, Ribeiro-Vaz I (2023) Motivation and knowledge of portuguese community pharmacists towards the reporting of suspected adverse reactions to medicines: A cross-sectional survey. *Journal of Community Health* 48(2): 295–308. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10900-022-01168-3>
- Gist-Mackey AN, Piercy CW, Bates JM (2024) Pharmacy work: Intrinsic motivation and extrinsic rewards across role and setting. *Journal of the American Pharmacists Association* 64(1): 104–110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.japh.2023.11.008>
- Grujicic M, Jovicic-Bata J, Radjen S, Novakovic B, Sipetic-Grujicic S (2016) Work motivation and job satisfaction of health workers in urban and rural areas. *Vojnosanitetski Pregled* 73(8): 735–743. <https://doi.org/10.2298/VSP140715062G>
- Hoat NV, Anh MK, Anh LNL, Thanh PTP, Thu LTH, Lien HQ (2024) Health care workers motivation and associated at Hanoi Medical University Hospital in 2023. *Hanoi Medical University - Journal of Medical Research (Vietnam)* 181(8): 102–112. <https://doi.org/10.52852/tcncyh.v181i8.2647>
- Kang A (2020) *Pharmacist Wellness and Mental Health Analysis*. Honors Thesis, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, Chapel Hill.
- Kumari K, Barkat Ali S, un Nisa Khan N, Abbas J (2021) Examining the Role of Motivation and Reward in Employees' Job Performance through Mediating Effect of Job Satisfaction: An Empirical Evidence. *International Journal of Organizational Leadership* 10(4): 401–420. <https://doi.org/10.33844/ijol.2021.60606>
- Le TTA, Ngo TKC, Vo TTT, Nguyen PBN, Nguyen TPT, Tran NMH, Le C (2024a) The factors affecting burnout among community pharmacists in Vietnam: a community-based cross-sectional study. *Hue Journal of Medicine and Pharmacy (Vietnam)* 14(6): 103. <https://doi.org/10.34071/jmp.2024.6.15>
- Le TTH, Nhan LC, Tran HB (2024b) Healthcare Human Resource Shortfall in Vietnam Compared to Select Countries in Asean. *Archives Des Sciences* 74(3): 258–264. <https://doi.org/10.62227/as/74339>
- Likhanov M, Maslennikova E, Costantini G, Budakova A, Esipenko E, Ismatullina V, Kovas Y (2022) This is the way: Network perspective on targets for spatial ability development programmes. *British Journal of Educational Psychology* 92(4): 1597–1620. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjep.12524>
- Malik AA, Yamamoto SS, Haque A, Butt NS, Baig M, Sauerborn R (2018) Developing and assessing a tool to measure motivation among physicians in Lahore, Pakistan. *PLoS ONE* 13(12): e0209546. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0209546>
- Matheson C, Bond CM (2011) Motivations for and barriers to community pharmacy services for drug misusers. *International Journal of Pharmacy Practice* 7(4): 256–263. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2042-7174.1999.tb00977.x>
- Ministry of Health of Vietnam (2025) Decision Promulgating the “Project on Strengthening the Training of Pharmacists in Clinical Pharmacy, Period 2025–2030 with a Vision to 2045”. Ministry of Health of Vietnam, Hanoi.
- Mkhitaryan S, Crutzen R, Steenaert E, de Vries NK (2019) Network approach in health behavior research: how can we explore new questions? *Health Psychology and Behavioral Medicine* 7(1): 362–384. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21642850.2019.1682587>
- Nguyen HTT, Dinh DX, Nguyen VM (2021) Knowledge, attitude and practices of community pharmacists regarding COVID-19: A paper-based survey in Vietnam. *PLoS ONE* 16(7): e0255420. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0255420>
- Nguyen NH, Le MT (2024) Enhancing competitiveness in traditional pharmacy business operations. *Journal of Science and Technology - Hoa Binh University (Vietnam)* 12(6): 18–26.
- Nwankwo ONO, Auer C, Oyo-Ita A, Eyers J, Wyss K, Fink G, Bosch-Capblanch X (2024) Human resources for health: a framework synthesis to put health workers at the centre of healthcare.

- BMJ Global Health 9(9): e014556. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2023-014556>
- O'Byrne R-M, Warren S (2022) Educational supervision, assessment and feedback for pharmacists. *Pharmaceutical Journal* 309(7963): 7963. <https://doi.org/10.1211/PJ.2022.1.148078>
- Our World in Data (n.d.) Pharmacists per 10,000 population, 2000 to 2022. https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/pharmaceutical-personnel-per-1000?tab=chart&country=VNM~OWID_WRL~THA~LAO~SGP~MYS~IDN~PHL
- Putra SW, Pono M, Wahda (2023) The effects of work stress and work motivation on employee performance. *Ilomata International Journal of Management* 4(3): 329–339. <https://doi.org/10.52728/ijm.v4i3.811>
- Raosoft Inc. (n.d.) Sample size calculator. [Retrieved 9 April 2025] <http://www.raosoft.com/samplesize.html>
- Saevels J, De Wulf I, Duquet N, De Rocker H (2023) Quality Care Program: Raise awareness, motivate and coach community-pharmacists to provide high-quality pharmaceutical care. *International Journal of Integrated Care* 23: 583. <https://doi.org/10.5334/ijic.ICIC23560>
- Saqr M, Beck E, López-Pernas S (2024) Psychological Networks: A Modern Approach to Analysis of Learning and Complex Learning Processes. In: Saqr M, López-Pernas S (Eds) *Learning Analytics Methods and Tutorials*. Springer, Cham, 639–671. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-54464-4_19
- Shin J, Grant AM (2019) Bored by interest: How intrinsic motivation in one task can reduce performance on other tasks. *Academy of Management Journal* 62(2): 415–436. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amj.2017.0735>
- Slimane NSB (2017) Motivation and Job Satisfaction of Pharmacists in Four Hospitals in Saudi Arabia. *Journal of Health Management* 19(1): 39–72. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0972063416682559>
- Stepanek S, Paul M (2023) Umbrella summary: Career interests. *Quality Improvement Center for Workforce Development*. <https://www.qicwd.org/umbrellasummary/career-interests>
- Tegegne E, Deml YA, Yirdaw G, Bewket Y (2024) Work motivation and factors associated with it among health professionals in Debre Markos Comprehensive Specialized Hospital. *Scientific Reports* 14(1): 2381. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-52409-5>
- Tran VD, Pham TT, Le TH, Thi TTN, Nguyen MT, Phan DP, Bui TBT, Nguyen MC, Dewey RS, Tran NT (2024) Workplace wellbeing in community pharmacy practice: A cross-sectional study in Can Tho, Vietnam. *AIMS Public Health* 11(1): 258–272. <https://doi.org/10.3934/publichealth.2024013>
- Vietdata's (2023) Pharmaceutical Retail Chains Industry Report: A new player enters the pharmaceutical retail chain market – Is there still room for growth? <https://www.vietdata.vn/post/a-new-player-enters-the-pharmaceutical-retail-chain-market-is-there-still-room-for-growth>
- Walker K, Carr AS, Wash A, Moczygemba LR (2025) Pharmacist perceptions of motivation and well-being using self-determination theory: A qualitative study. *Journal of the American Pharmacists Association* 65(2): 102321. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.japh.2024.102321>
- Weiß M, Gründahl M, Deckert J, Eichner FA, Kohls M, Störk S, Heuschmann PU, Hein G, Gelbrich G, Weißbrich B, Dölken L, Kurzai O, Ertl G, Barth M, Morbach C (2023) Differential network interactions between psychosocial factors, mental health, and health-related quality of life in women and men. *Scientific Reports* 13(1): 11642. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-38525-8>
- Willis-Shattuck M, Bidwell P, Thomas S, Wyness L, Blaauw D, Ditlopo P (2008) Motivation and retention of health workers in developing countries: a systematic review. *BMC Health Services Research* 8(1): 247. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6963-8-247>
- World Health Organization (n.d.) Health workforce. https://www.who.int/health-topics/health-workforce#tab=tab_1
- Zhang Y, Yuan Z, Cheng T, Wang C, Li J (2023) Intrinsic drive of medical staff: a survey of employee representatives from 22 hospitals in China. *Frontiers in Psychology* 14: 1157823. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1157823>